

Investigation of Microbial Contamination in Local Chicken Slaughtered in Babylon

Hashim Hadi Al-Jebory
Agriculture College, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Mohammed Khalil Ibrahim Al-Saeedi
College of Environmental Sciences, Al-Qasim Green University, Iraq

Duaa Mohammad Ali Annooz
*Department of Animal Production Technologies, Kufa Technical Institute,
Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University*

Rasha Fajer Al-Jebory
*Department of Medical Biotechnology, College of Science,
Al-Mustaqbal University, 51001, Babylon, Iraq*

Article History:

Received: 22.10.2025 Revised: 18.11.2025 Accepted: 19.11.2025 Published: 22.11.2025

Abstract

Local chicken slaughtering sites are considered the most common places for the growth and reproduction of pathogenic bacteria that have a direct relationship with humans and their health, which raises the concern of many authors due to the health implications that may cause harm to consumers. Six local chicken slaughtering sites were identified in different parts of Babylon Governorate and samples were taken from them during four months (January, February, March and April). Samples were taken using transport media tubes containing peptone water for preserving the samples. The examination was general for each site and specific by tests (slaughter site, chicken plucker machine, tools, water and carcass). The results showed bacterial contamination with total bacteria (TB), *E. coli* (EC), *Salmonella* (SA), *Pseudomonas* (PS) and *Shigella* (SH). TB increased significantly in the slaughtering site and total *E. coli* bacteria increased significantly in the chicken plucker machine, while the logarithmic number of *Pseudomonas* bacteria increased significantly in the slaughtering site and chicken plucker machine, as for *Salmonella*, it increased in the place of skinning and water and the morale of the *Shigella* increased in the slaughter place.

Keywords: *microbial contamination, local chicken slaughtered, Healthy meat, sustainable agriculture.*

Suggested citation: Al-Jebory, H.H., Al-Saeedi, M.K.I., Annooz, D.M.A., & Al-Jebory, R.F. (2025). Investigation of Microbial Contamination in Local Chicken Slaughtered in Babylon. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 3(6), 167-173. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3\(6\).16](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2025.3(6).16)

Introduction

The slaughter line is made up of processing stages that perform various slaughter and carcass preparation operations, often in circular systems: stunning, bleeding, scalding, plucking, evisceration, washing, and chilling. Slaughter

speeds are typically 4,000 to 13,000 per hour, and conventional broiler slaughter is highly automated and requires minimal manual labor compared to cattle slaughter (Mataragas et al., 2012). The main challenge facing large-scale broiler slaughter is to minimize meat contamination by maintaining good hygiene of

the operations (Mataragas et al., 2012). It exhibits uniform shapes and therefore carcass sizes are important for machines to perform as intended and to limit bacterial contamination, particularly from feces on the meat (Soro et al., 2020). Live chickens arriving for slaughter are mainly determined by the bacterial environment on the farm (Ghareeb et al., 2013). Avoiding pathogens on the farm is a major challenge as well as in the slaughterhouse. Slaughterhouses can compensate and reduce bacterial loads on poultry carcasses to Good hygiene practices, HACCP, Additionally, several measures are required to lessen the amount of bacteria that contaminates carcass surfaces (Nastasijević et al., 2020). Microbiological tests are conducted in accordance with practical hygiene standards to monitor and regulate the bacterial burdens on carcasses in slaughterhouses (Anon, 2017). The most frequent causes of bacterial gastroenteritis in Europe are *Salmonella* infections, which are mostly linked to meat consumption (EFSA, 2021). Healthy birds are hard to spot on the farm since they might shed both diseases. None of these are detected by visual inspection of meat, and the establishment of an integrated food safety assurance system can be achieved by improving food chain information (FCI), To enhance meat safety monitoring and control in the production of chicken meat, risk-based interventions are crucial (Lupo et al., 2013). By preventing or minimizing the spread of infections and pathogens from feathers and intestines to carcasses, slaughterhouses are attempting to increase the safety of chicken meat with regard to *Salmonella* and pathogenic bacteria; in other words, the butchering process is one of the most crucial methods of hygiene (Buncic et al., 2017). Some nations, like Iraq, employ *E. Coli* as a marker of bacterial contamination on chicken carcasses in addition to keeping an eye out for *Salmonella* (EFSA, 2021). The European Food Safety Authority has recommended and explored the use of indicator bacteria, including *Salmonella*, Shigellosis, *Pseudomonas*, *Escherichia coli*, and Enterobacteriaceae, as practical hygiene standards in livestock (EFSA, 2021). More than 600 million individuals, or almost one in ten people, fell ill in 2010 after eating tainted food,

and 420,000 of them died, including 125,000 children under the age of five, according to Hoffmann et al. (2017). Additionally, during food preparation or slaughter, animal-based foods may become contaminated with microorganisms (İnanç and Mustafa, 2018). These pathogens come into touch with food during slaughter, storage, and packaging. Therefore, the current study intends to assess the amount of bacterial contamination in local chicken slaughterhouses in Babylon state.

Materials

This study was conducted to evaluate bacterial contamination in six local chicken slaughterhouses, 72 samples were collected over a period of four months, divided into 18 samples each month, three samples for each of the six sites specified in Babil Governorate. The samples were divided according to the local site into (L1, L2, L3, L4, L5, and L6) during the period January 2024–April 2024. The samples were collected from six local slaughterhouses situated throughout Babil Governorate. Media Transporter tubes with peptone water were used to transport, collect, and preserve samples from slaughterhouses before transporting them to the laboratory. The sample transporter has a validity of 24 hours. The samples were examined according to the method of (Rai, 2016) and using the inverted plate method, macckonkey agar and Nutrient agar were used, as well as EMB agar, and *Pseudomonas* agar is a selective culture medium for bacteria, as well as S-S agar is a selective culture medium for bacteria, wherein 1 milliliter of each carrier sample was extracted and put into a Petri dish. Then, the designated medium was added, stirring clockwise and counterclockwise to guarantee homogeneity, and the dish was incubated inverted at 37°C for 48 hours. Following this, the samples were identified based on the culture media.

SAS, (2012) was use to analysis data and Duncan, (1955) test used to significant appearance in slaughter local parameters.

Results and Discussion

Total Count

Table 1: shown the study result through January month, noted in L1 the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH was found to be contaminated with a logarithmic number of (345×10^3 , 95×10^3 , 21×10^3 , 10×10^3 , 30×10^3 respectively), while in L2 was found the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (269×10^3 , 86×10^3 , 32×10^3 , 11×10^3 , 27×10^3 respectively), in L3 the logarithmic number of

the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (301×10^3 , 112×10^3 , 18×10^3 , 8×10^3 , 25×10^3 respectively), at same time in L4 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (256×10^3 , 123×10^3 , 35×10^3 , 9×10^3 , 28×10^3 respectively), so as in L5 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (314×10^3 , 91×10^3 , 14×10^3 , 15×10^3 , 21×10^3 respectively), meanwhile in L6 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (145×10^3 , 101×10^3 , 29×10^3 , 21×10^3 , 32×10^3 respectively).

Table 1. Investigation of Microbial Contamination in Chicken Slaughtered in Babylon Stat (January)

Sample NO.	TB	Total EC	PS	SA	SH
L1	345×10^3	95×10^3	21×10^3	10×10^3	30×10^3
L2	269×10^3	86×10^3	32×10^3	11×10^3	27×10^3
L3	301×10^3	112×10^3	18×10^3	8×10^3	25×10^3
L4	256×10^3	123×10^3	35×10^3	9×10^3	28×10^3
L5	314×10^3	91×10^3	14×10^3	15×10^3	21×10^3
L6	145×10^3	101×10^3	29×10^3	21×10^3	32×10^3

Table 2: explain the study result through February month, in L1 the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH was found to be contaminated with a logarithmic number of (124×10^3 , 51×10^3 , 21×10^3 , 5×10^3 , 8×10^3 respectively), while in L2 was found the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (56×10^3 , 47×10^3 , 8×10^3 , 6×10^3 , 11×10^3 respectively), in L3 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (201×10^3 , 81×10^3 , 11×10^3 , 12×10^3 , 11×10^3 respectively), at

same time in L4 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (174×10^3 , 95×10^3 , 31×10^3 , 24×10^3 , 5×10^3 respectively), in L5 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (156×10^3 , 36×10^3 , 14×10^3 , 13×10^3 , 9×10^3 respectively), meanwhile in L6 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (89×10^3 , 73×10^3 , 10×10^3 , 15×10^3 , 7×10^3 respectively).

Table 2. Investigation of Microbial Contamination in Chicken Slaughtered in Babylon stat (February)

Sample NO.	TB	Total EC	PS	SA	SH
L1	124×10^3	51×10^3	21×10^3	5×10^3	8×10^3
L2	56×10^3	47×10^3	8×10^3	6×10^3	11×10^3
L3	201×10^3	81×10^3	11×10^3	12×10^3	11×10^3
L4	174×10^3	95×10^3	31×10^3	24×10^3	5×10^3
L5	156×10^3	36×10^3	14×10^3	13×10^3	9×10^3
L6	89×10^3	73×10^3	10×10^3	15×10^3	7×10^3

Table 3: shown the study result through March month, noted in L1 the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH was found to be contaminated with a logarithmic number of (243×10^3 , 122×10^3 , 47×10^3 , 26×10^3 , 22×10^3 respectively), in L2 was found the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH

(309×10^3 , 136×10^3 , 52×10^3 , 17×10^3 , 16×10^3 respectively), in L3 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (247×10^3 , 78×10^3 , 91×10^3 , 24×10^3 , 21×10^3 respectively), in L4 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (291×10^3 , 108×10^3 , 42×10^3 ,

19×10³, 19×10³ respectively), in L5 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (431×10³, 149×10³, 72×10³, 22×10³, 22×10³ respectively), meanwhile in L6 the

logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (145×10³, 101×10³, 29×10³, 21×10³, 32×10³ respectively).

Table 3. Investigation of Microbial Contamination in Chicken Slaughtered in Babylon stat (March)

Sample NO.	TB	Total EC	PS	SA	SH
L1	243×10 ³	122×10 ³	47×10 ³	26×10 ³	22×10 ³
L2	309×10 ³	136×10 ³	52×10 ³	17×10 ³	16×10 ³
L3	247×10 ³	78×10 ³	91×10 ³	24×10 ³	21×10 ³
L4	291×10 ³	108×10 ³	42×10 ³	19×10 ³	19×10 ³
L5	431×10 ³	149×10 ³	72×10 ³	22×10 ³	22×10 ³
L6	365×10 ³	137×10 ³	34×10 ³	23×10 ³	12×10 ³

Table 4: Reviews the results of the study in April month, noted in L1 the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH was found to be contaminated with a logarithmic number of (200×10³, 82×10³, 56×10³, 5×10³, 13×10³ respectively), while in L2 was found the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (198×10³, 69×10³, 32×10³, 11×10³, 9×10³ respectively), in L3 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (214×10³, 71×10³, 41×10³, 13×10³, 6×10³ respectively), at

same time in L4 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (251×10³, 95×10³, 47×10³, 21×10³, 8×10³ respectively), so as in L5 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (232×10³, 63×10³, 29×10³, 8×10³, 31×10³ respectively), meanwhile in L6 the logarithmic number of the TB, total EC, PS, SA, and SH (181×10³, 57×10³, 18×10³, 4×10³, 15×10³ respectively).

Table 4. Investigation of Microbial Contamination in Chicken Slaughtered in Babylon stat (April)

Sample NO.	TB	Total EC	PS	SA	SH
L1	200×10 ³	82×10 ³	56×10 ³	5×10 ³	13×10 ³
L2	198×10 ³	69×10 ³	32×10 ³	11×10 ³	9×10 ³
L3	214×10 ³	71×10 ³	41×10 ³	13×10 ³	6×10 ³
L4	251×10 ³	95×10 ³	47×10 ³	21×10 ³	8×10 ³
L5	232×10 ³	63×10 ³	29×10 ³	8×10 ³	31×10 ³
L6	181×10 ³	57×10 ³	18×10 ³	4×10 ³	15×10 ³

Slaughter Local Parameters

TB

In figure 1: noted the investigated of TB contamination in slaughter local, the TB significant (P<0.05) increase in slaughter place and water respectively compared to chicken plucker machine, tools, and carcass, while chicken plucker machine, and tools significant (P<0.05) increase on carcass.

Figure 1. Investigation of Total Bacteria in Different Places of Chicken Slaughter in Babylon Stat

E. coli

In figure 2: noted the investigated of total *E. coli* contamination in slaughter local, the total *E. coli* significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in slaughter place compared to chicken plucker machine, tools, carcass, and water, while chicken plucker machine, tools, and water significant ($P < 0.05$) increase compared to carcass.

Figure 2. Investigation of Total *E. Coli* in Different Places of Chicken Slaughter in Babylon Stat

PS

Figure 3: shown the PS count contamination in slaughter local, the total PS significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in slaughter place, and tools compared to chicken plucker machine, carcass, and water, while chicken plucker machine, and water significant ($P < 0.05$) increase on carcass.

Figure 3. Investigation of *Pesudomonas* in Different Places of Chicken Slaughter in Babylon Stat

SA

Figure 4: shown the SA count in slaughter local, the SA significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in water, compared to slaughter place, chicken plucker machine, carcass, and water, while slaughter place, chicken plucker machine, and water significant ($P < 0.05$) increase on carcass.

Figure 4. Investigation of *Salmonella* in Different Places of Chicken Slaughter in Babylon Stat

SH

In figure 5: noted the investigated of SH contamination in slaughter local, the SH significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in slaughter place compared to chicken plucker machine, tools, carcass, and water.

Figure 5. Investigation of *Shigella* in Different Places of Chicken Slaughter in Babylon Stat

The high number of bacteria in local slaughterhouses is due to the fact that these places are a suitable environment for the growth and reproduction of bacteria, as many studies have indicated the occurrence of bacterial contamination in local Babylon slaughterhouses (Al-Saeedi et al., 2024). Bacteria are also transferred from broiler breeding halls to slaughterhouses, as it was found that a gram of broiler breeding hall dust contains 30,000 *E. coli* bacteria (Elsagheer et al., 2024). This is transferred through the feathers and body of the broiler to the slaughterhouses. When skinning, blood is considered an effective nutritional medium for the growth of bacteria, which explains the high number of them in the skinning place, which causes the transmission of pathogens to consumers (Ovuru et al., 2023). The high concentrations of harmful germs in meat may be caused by improper carcass processing, cleanliness, and slaughtering practices. Meat quality prior to slaughter and processing, as well as the cleanliness of slaughterhouses, prep rooms, and marketing facilities, are typically significantly impacted by the amount of bacteria found on carcasses. Only healthy and typically clean animals should be killed in order to assure meat safety, and it can be difficult to produce clean, pathogen-free meat from sick and unclean animals (Vidyarthi et al., 2021). Contact with meat surfaces, including hardwood tables, cutting blades, weighing scales, the hands and clothes of meat handlers outside slaughterhouses, and water-holding devices including metal and plastic containers, carts, and meat elevators, can result in bacterial contamination. As a result, a sample's bacterial count is frequently used to gauge its possible harm to people (Yu et al., 2022). When slaughterhouses are not properly controlled, they can contribute significantly to microbial contamination (Hauge et al., 2023). It has been reported that approximately 30% of the total population in industrialized countries suffer from foodborne illnesses annually (Devleesschauwer et al., 2018). The use of contaminated and unsterilized water for cleaning and washing carcasses increases the transmission of pathogens. Several studies have indicated that water is one of the sources of microbial

contamination, especially SA and *E. coli* (Buncic et al., 2017).

Conclusion

It is concluded from the results of the study that there is high bacterial contamination in local slaughterhouses in Babylon, due to poor hygiene and lack of health care for slaughtered animals, which makes them a source of risk for the transmission of diseases to consumers. Therefore, it is recommended that the authorities and regulatory bodies monitor the slaughtering sites and implement health conditions that limit the growth of bacteria.

References

- Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., Hussein, H. M., & Al-Jebory, H. H. (2024). Study of microbiological contamination in Babylonian ruminant and poultry slaughter. *International Journal of Life Science and Agriculture Research*, 3(11), 890–897. <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijlsar/V03I11Y2024-08>
- Boysen, L., Nauta, M., & Rosenquist, H. (2016). *Campylobacter* spp. and *Escherichia coli* contamination of broiler carcasses across the slaughter line in Danish slaughterhouses. *Microbial Risk Analysis*, 2–3, 63–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mran.2016.05.005>
- Bunčić, A., Antić, D., & Blagojević, B. (2017). Microbial ecology of poultry and poultry products. In *Quantitative Microbiology in Food Processing* (pp. 483–498). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118823071.ch24>
- Devleesschauwer, B., Haagsma, J. A., Mangen, M.-J. J., Lake, R. J., & Havelaar, A. H. (2018). The global burden of foodborne disease. In T. Roberts (Ed.), *Food Safety Economics: Incentives for a Safer Food Supply* (pp. 107–122). Cham, Switzerland: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-92138-9_7
- Elsagheer, M. A., Al-Saeedi, M. K. I., Al-Jebory, H. H., Al-Jebory, R. F., & Eletma, M. R. (2024). Exogenous melatonin enhances carcass traits, litter condition, and well-being of broilers exposed to heat stress. *Chelonian Conservation and Biology*, 19(1), 1306–1330.
- European Commission. (2017). *Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/1495 of 23 August 2017*

amending Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005 as regards *Campylobacter* in broiler carcasses (Official Journal of the European Union). Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/1495/oj>

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) & European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). (2021). *EU One Health 2020 zoonoses report*. *EFSA Journal*, 19(12), 6971. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6971>

Ghareeb, K., Awad, W. A., Mohnl, M., Schatzmayr, G., & Böhm, J. (2013). Control strategies for *Campylobacter* infection in poultry production. *World's Poultry Science Journal*, 69(1), 57–76. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0043933913000056>

Hauge, S. J., Johannessen, G. S., Haverkamp, T. H. A., Bjørkøy, S., Llaraena, A. K., Spilberg, B., Leithaug, M., Økland, M., Holthe, J., & Røtterud, O.-J. (2023). Assessment of poultry process hygiene and bacterial dynamics along two broiler slaughter lines in Norway. *Food Control*, 146, 109526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109526>

Hemalata, V. B., & Virupakshaiah, D. B. M. (2016). Isolation and identification of food-borne pathogens from spoiled food samples. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 5(6), 1017–1025. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2016.506.108>

Hoffmann, S., Devleeschauwer, B., Aspinall, W., et al. (2017). Attribution of global foodborne disease to specific foods: findings from a World Health Organization structured expert elicitation. *PLoS ONE*, 12(9), e0183641. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0183641>

İnanç, A., & Mustafa, A. S. (2018). Antibiotic resistance of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 isolated from chicken meats. *KSÜ Doğa Bilimleri Dergisi*, 21, 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.18016/ksudobil.289192>

Lupo, C., le Bouquin, S., Balaine, L., Michel, V., Péraste, J., Petetin, I., Colin, P., Jouffe, L., & Chauvin, C. (2013). Bayesian network as an aid for Food Chain Information use for meat

inspection. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, 109(1), 25–36.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prevetmed.2012.09.004>

Mataragas, M., Drosinos, E. H., Tsola, E., & Zoiopoulos, P. E. (2012). Integrating statistical process control to monitor and improve carcass quality in a poultry slaughterhouse implementing a HACCP system. *Food Control*, 28(2), 205–211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2012.05.032>

Nastasijević, I., Proscia, F., Bošković, M., Glišić, M., Blagojević, B., Sorgentone, S., Kirbiš, A., & Ferri, M. (2020). The European Union control strategy for *Campylobacter* spp. in the broiler meat chain. *Journal of Food Safety*, 40(5), e12819. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfs.12819>

Ovuru, K. F., Izah, S. C., Ogidi, O. I., Imarhiagbe, O., & Ogwu, M. C. (2023). Slaughterhouse facilities in developing nations: sanitation and hygiene practices, microbial contaminants and sustainable management system. *Food Science and Biotechnology*, 33(3), 519–537. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10068-023-01406-x>

Rai, B. K. (2016). *Basic Practical Manual on Industrial Microbiology*. Lulu.com.

Soro, A. B., Whyte, P., Bolton, D. J., & Tiwari, B. K. (2020). Strategies and novel technologies to control *Campylobacter* in the poultry chain: a review. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 19, 1353–1577. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12544>

Vidyarthi, S., Vaddella, V., Cao, N., Kuppu, S., & Pandey, P. (2021). Pathogens in animal carcasses and the efficacy of rendering for pathogen inactivation in rendered products: A review. *Future Foods*, 3, 100010.

Yu, Z., Jung, D., Park, S., Hu, Y., Huang, K., Rasco, B. A., Wang, S., Ronholm, J., Lu, X., & Chen, J. (2022). Smart traceability for food safety. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 62(4), 905–916. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1830262>

